

Measurement of the variation of interfacial shear stress in Ti/SiC composites as a function of temperature

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Summary: Ti-6Al-4V/SiC fibre reinforced composites have been identified for use in aeroengine applications that typically experience temperatures of ~ 350 °C in service. Critical to their performance is the interfacial shear strength between matrix and fibres. We have used X-ray synchrotron strain mapping to monitor the variation in axial fibre strain in a single fragmented fibre in a Ti-6Al-4V matrix at 25, 125 and 250°C. The variation in interfacial shear stress along the fibre/matrix interface was inferred from the rate of change of the fibre strain along the fibre. In this way the frictional sliding stress of a pristine fibre interface was evaluated as a function of temperature.

Keywords: Ti, SiC, composite, fragmentation test, interfacial shear stress, temperature, frictional sliding

Introduction

Ti-6Al-4V/SiC fibre reinforced composites are being developed for use in the compressor section of aeroengines, being limited to applications where the temperatures do not rise above 350°C (Hooker and Doorbar 2000). Within this temperature range their improved elevated temperature strength and creep resistance allow considerable weight savings ($\sim 40\%$) over conventional Ti bladed disc designs.

It has been recognised for many years that the mechanical behaviour of fibre reinforced composites is crucially dependent on the properties of the fibre/matrix interface. Several micromechanical tests, have been designed to measure fibre/matrix interfacial properties of composite materials, the most frequently used being full-fragmentation, microindentation and pull-out [1-4]. We have developed a variant on the single fibre full-fragmentation test in which the fragmentation process is monitored in situ by synchrotron X-ray diffraction to follow the development of elastic fibre strain in the fractured segments [5,6]. This method has the advantage over the original test that it uses the gradient in fibre strain along the fibre to deduce the interfacial shear stress and is thus not dependent on the fibre fracture strength, which has been found to fall markedly upon first fracture due to the introduction of defects [7]. To date there have been a large number of measurements of the Ti-6Al-4V/SiC interfacial properties as summarised in [8], mostly for pristine SCS6 SiC fibres at room temperature. These point to a frictional sliding mechanism with an interface strength of between 100 and 200MPa, which falls dramatically due to fretting in the vicinity of a fatigue crack. The stresses recorded in this region vary along the fibre length [8,9] and this complicates the measuring of a representative value. Nevertheless interfacial strengths of fatigued interfaces as low as 8MPa at room temperature falling to 2MPa at 500C have been inferred from fatigue studies in SCS6/Ti-6Al-4V [10] and SCS6/Timetal [11]. To date there have been very few measurements primarily for Timetal 834 and 21S of the pristine interfacial properties of SCS6 SiC at elevated temperature [12-14]. The variation in interface stress is important from a practical viewpoint. If the sliding occurs by Coulomb friction, then one would expect the interfacial sliding stress to fall with increasing temperature due to a

reduction in the radial clamping force [14-15]. The aim of this paper is to determine the strength of the pristine SCS-6 SiC/Ti-6Al-4V interface as a function of temperature.

Experimental

We have applied a modified single fibre fragmentation test to profile the elastic response along the fibre, using high energy synchrotron X-ray diffraction [5]. In this way we can determine the interfacial shear stress variation during in-situ loading experiments. High energy synchrotron X-rays are sufficiently penetrating that the elastic fibre strain (ε_f) can be measured as a function of position (z) along the embedded fibre non-destructively. The fibre strain at a location z is determined from the change in lattice spacing, d , measured in terms of the shift in the diffraction peak position $\theta - \theta_0$ relative to the stress free Bragg angle θ_0 :

$$\varepsilon_f(z) = \frac{d(z) - d_0}{d_0} = -\cot \theta_0 \frac{\theta(z) - \theta_0}{\theta_0} \quad [1]$$

Unlike the conventional fragmentation test, the best results are obtained when the fibre is only partially fragmented because in this case the fragments are long and the gradients easily measured. The interfacial shear stress at a location along the fibre is evaluated directly from stress balance:

$$\tau = \frac{E_f r_f}{2} \cdot \frac{d\varepsilon_f}{dz} \quad [2]$$

where r_f is the fibre radius, E_f is the fibre modulus and z is the distance along the fibre.

Model single fibre composites were fabricated by hot pressing (at ~ 900 °C) single, isolated 3M Ti-6Al-4V matrix-coated ($3 \mu\text{m}$ coating) SCS6 fibres between two sheets of Ti-6Al-4V. Dumbbell samples, as shown in figure 1a, were cut from the panel using electro-discharge machining, such that a single fibre was aligned parallel to the tensile loading axis.

Figure 1 a) Schematic representation of single fibre composite sample (all dimensions in mm), b) photograph of the in situ thermomechanical loading rig.

Mechanical testing was carried out at 25, 125 and 245 °C on a custom built high temperature tensile straining rig (Figure 1b), equipped with a 2 kN load cell. The sample was mounted in the rig, such that the fibre axis was parallel to the direction of crosshead displacement. The load and the crosshead displacement were controlled by computer. Deformation was applied in increments until fibre fragmentation occurred. In the results section the deformation stages are identified in terms of temperature and nominal applied loads (σ_{app}).

The rig was designed to transfer heat to the sample via heated grips. The temperature was monitored via k-type thermocouples, one embedded in each grip and one kept in contact with the center of the sample via a spring clip.

Synchrotron X-ray diffraction measurements were made, at each deformation stage, on the ID11 beamline at the European Synchrotron Research Facility (ESRF). The schematic representation of the setup is shown in figure 2 below. The energy of the X-ray beam energy chosen for the experiment was 55 keV. The beam was focused vertically to have a spatial resolution of 10 μ m in the longitudinal direction of the fibre. In the horizontal direction, transverse to the fibre direction, incident slits were used to stop the beam down to a width of 200 μ m. A Frelon CCD camera, situated 1.44 m away from the sample was used to collect the diffraction pattern. Measurements were made in transmission, with the camera positioned such that it was in line with the sample, but offset vertically, so as to capture a segment at the top of the (110) SiC diffraction ring. With the axis of the loading rig vertical, shifts in this part of the diffraction pattern correspond to changes in axial fibre strain (ϵ_r) according to equation (1). The rig was mounted on an x-y-z stage, allowing translation of the sample through the incident beam such that measurements could be made at discrete points along the SCS6 fibre length. In this way the axial fibre strain was measured at 10 μ m intervals, each measurement taking 1 second.

Figure 2 Schematic showing the relative positions of sample, slits and detector; the sample was then translated vertically to map the axial strain variation along the fibre (not to scale).

It was not possible to deduce the stress-free lattice spacing d_0 for the (110) SiC-reflection from an unstressed composite sample because of the prior residual thermal stresses. Instead the lattice spacing at room temperature (25°C) at the point of a fibre break, i.e. after fragmentation, was taken to be stress free. If Poisson strains are neglected, the axial fibre strain can be assumed to be effectively zero across the broken fibre end.

The thermal and mechanical loading cycle can be divided into the following stages:

- i) initial plastic straining until fibre fragmentation corresponding to a load of 1150 MPa
- ii) unloading followed by increase in temperature to approximately 125°C
- iii) plastic straining to a load of 800 MPa
- iv) unloading followed by increase in temperature to approximately 245°C
- v) further straining to a load of 250 MPa

With increasing temperature the stress-free lattice parameter increases and this must be taken into account in order to calculate the elastic strain. The stress free lattice spacing increases by $d_0\alpha_f\Delta T$ where α_f is the coefficient of thermal expansion of the fibre ($4.1 \times 10^{-6}/K$) [16] and ΔT the temperature increment in Kelvin. In this case the stress-free lattice spacing at temperature was taken to be that which gives zero strain at the fibre ends. The thermal expansions needed to achieve this in the two cases corresponded to 120 °C and 242 °C which compare well with the corresponding thermocouple measurements of 125°C and 245°C respectively.

Results and discussion

Fibre Strain Profiles

The point-to-point fibre strain distributions measured along a single SCS6 fibre embedded in a Ti-6Al-4V matrix are shown in figure 3. The four data sets correspond to the fibre strain distribution; prior to sample deformation at 25°C, then after fibre fragmentation and in the loaded condition at 25, 125 & 245°C. At each temperature, the load was increased until plastic straining had been introduced. The purpose of doing this was to ensure that fibre/matrix interface attained the sliding condition. This explains the occurrence of a new fibre break in fragment 6 at 125 °C.

Figure 3 Variation of elastic fibre strain, ϵ_f , measured along an SCS6 fibre embedded in a Ti-6Al-4V matrix, prior to and after fibre fragmentation (at 25, 125 and 245 °C). The loads in each case are also shown on the graph.

At 25°C it can be seen that elastic fibre strain in the undeformed sample is compressive along

the whole of the gauge length. The residual compressive strain varies along the gauge length and is highest between $z = 3$ to $z = 5$ mm, reaching a maximum of around -3200×10^{-6} . This residual strain arises as a consequence of the thermal expansion misfit between the fibres and matrix, the processing temperature, the opportunity for stress relaxation and the volume fractions of each phase. With only a single fibre the misfit is accommodated primarily in the fibre. This explains why the strain is double that observed for 35 vol% fibre containing material [17], but more in line with other lower fibre volume fraction containing materials [6,12]. In fact, if the difference in coefficient of thermal expansion between the phases is around $6 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$ then the residual strain is equivalent to a temperature drop of around 530 °C. This is essentially the increment in temperature ΔT_{esf} required to make the composite effectively stress free. The reason for the variability of residual stress along the length of the fibre is almost certainly due to the fabrication process.

The characteristic shape of the fibre strain profile after room temperature straining indicates that fibre fragmentation has occurred and that the fibre has broken in 7 places along the gauge length (approximately at $z = 1.15, 1.7, 2.13, 3.2, 3.7, 5.2$ & 5.5), defining 6 full fragments and 2 partial fragments (at either end of the gauge length). The fragments are numbered 1 to 8 starting at $z = 0$.

The fibre strain distribution in each fragment is approximately triangular in shape. The triangular form first observed by Kelly and Tyson [18] is indicative of a constant level of stress transfer, in this case taking place by the mechanism of frictional sliding. This mechanism is consistent with the observations of numerous other studies for SCS6 fibres in Ti matrices [5,13,14,17].

At elevated temperature, it can be seen that the elastic strain profiles have a similar triangular shape to that seen at room temperature. However, at 125 °C, even though the displacement applied to the sample was greater than at 25 °C, the slope of the fibre strain distribution and hence the maximum fibre strain is lower in each fragment. This effect is more pronounced at 245 °C, even though the applied plastic strain has been increased still further. This suggests that in each case the rate of increase in fibre strain (i.e. the strain gradient) is at a maximum. The associated reduction in the capability for stress transfer from the matrix to the fibre is responsible for the reduced peak fibre strains.

Interfacial shear stress

The relationship given in Equation 2 has been used to derive the shear stress distribution along the fibre/matrix interface from the rate of change of fibre strain, at room temperature in Figure 4. The individual data points have been obtained from equation 2 by calculating the point-to-point strain gradient, $d\varepsilon_f/dz$, while the curve has been derived by taking the average gradient over 4 successive points.

Generally, it can be seen that the interfacial shear stress, builds up over a very short distance (<0.1 mm) from a fragment end towards an approximately constant plateau value, τ_f . This is maintained almost to the centre of each fragment indicating that the non sliding region is very short, c.f. the classical form shown inset in figure 4. It is not clear whether the point-to-point scatter or the variation in the plateau levels are indicative of real changes in the local interfacial stress, but it is known that the interface is not smooth at this scale (the standard deviation calculated from the point-to-point scatter corresponds to $\sim \pm 55$ MPa). There is no clear evidence of sharp peaks between the flat sliding region and the perfectly bonded region

as would be expected if there was a strong mechanical or chemical bond which must be

Figure 4 Variation of interfacial shear stress along the SCS6 fibre embedded in a Ti-6Al-4V matrix, after fibre fragmentation at room temperature (25 °C). The dash-dot line shows the average frictional interfacial shear stress calculated from individual data points in the sliding regions. The vertical lines denote the ends of fibre fragments, while the schematic inset under fragment 4 shows the classical frictional sliding response with a short perfectly bonded region at the centre.

overcome prior to sliding. However it is possible that because of the way the fibre progressively fragments that even those regions not currently sliding at the centers of the fragments, were sliding at an earlier stage when there were less fragments. The dashed lines represent the 67 % confidence limits on the frictional sliding stress and equates to $\tau_f \sim 150 \pm 25$ MPa. By comparison, Preuss et al [5,7] found for the same system and same test methods that $\tau_f = 200$ MPa. This correlation is very reasonable when considered in the context of wide ranging values produced in recent years in other studies on Ti/SiC composites [6]. For some unknown reason the negative sliding stresses appear to be lower than the positive ones.

The variation in interfacial shear stress profile as a function of temperature is shown in figure 5 using the gradients calculated over 4 successive fibre strain data-points. At each temperature the trends are the same, although it is clear that the frictional sliding stress falls dramatically with increasing temperature. The dashed lines are an estimate of τ_f derived by taking an average of the plateau values over all of the fragments (as described above).

The reduction in frictional sliding stress with increasing temperature can, at least in part, be attributed to a reduction of radial clamping (normal) stresses acting on the fibre, originally generated as a result of thermal contraction during cooling from processing temperatures. It would be expected that a reduced stress normal to the fibre will decrease the interfacial shear stress and hence reduce the efficiency of stress transfer from fibre to the matrix. The results presented here strongly support this hypothesis.

Figure 5 Interfacial shear stress profiles under a tensile load (σ_{app}) along the fragmented SCS6 fibre as a function of temperature. The horizontal dashed lines represent the average plateau levels for the three temperatures. The vertical lines denote the ends of the fibre fragments.

In a previous study [14] using push-out testing of fibres in very thin slices a constant ratio of 0.4 was found between the average clamping radial stress and the maximum local shear stress for SCS6 in Ti-24-11 and Ti-5-3 matrices. Connell and Zok noted a Coulomb friction constant of 0.4 for sigma fibres in Ti-6Al-4V [10]. In our case the radial stresses are likely to be around 330 MPa given the axial thermal residual misfit stresses and the very low volume fraction [15]. This would put the room temperature frictional coefficient at around 0.45 in good correspondence with the above and values around 0.5-0.6 found elsewhere [5,7]. Since the thermal residual clamping stress is proportional to $\Delta\alpha\Delta T_{esf}$, where ΔT_{esf} corresponds to the equivalent temperature drop needed to create the original residual stresses one would expect the sliding force to fall to zero when the temperature is raised above the equivalent temperature (530°C), if friction due to asperity contact is neglected. As a consequence it is somewhat surprising the rate at which the interfacial shear stress falls points towards attaining zero shear stress at a temperature of only around 300°C.

Strains upon unloading

The residual strain profile along fragment 4 after unloading is shown in figure 6a. It takes the form of a characteristic ‘w’ profile, previously reported by Preuss *et al* [5] and modelled by Rauchs *et al* [6]. In brief, the profile arises because reverse sliding initiates at each end and moves progressively towards the centre, causing the apex of the original triangle (the profile of which is indicated by the dotted line) to fall to lower strains. The boundaries between the reverse sliding regions near the ends and the originally forward sliding regions near the centre are marked by the two symmetric reversals of gradient at the two basal points of the ‘w’. Comparing the 25 °C and 125 °C profiles it can be seen that elastic strain gradients at 125 °C are lower than at 25 °C.

Figure 6 The fibre strain distributions for (a) fragment 4 and (b) fragment 2 at 25 °C ($\sigma_{app} \sim 12$ MPa) and 125 °C ($\sigma_{app} \sim 12$ MPa) after unloading of the fragmented sample (the y-scale is shared). The dotted line in part (a) indicates the shape of the strain profile along the fragment during the loading stage, as shown in figure 4.

This is further evidence of the lowering of frictional sliding stress with increasing temperature. The gradients on the unloading graph appear to correspond to interfacial shear stresses around two thirds of those for the forward loaded case. In addition it is interesting to note that, as illustrated in figure 6b, not all fragments exhibit the residual ‘w’ profile when unloaded. The shorter fragments all seem to relax to a ‘v’ profile. This can also be observed in Figure 9a of Rauchs *et al* [6]. While these observations show that the resistance to fibre sliding in the reverse direction appears to be easier at the fragment ends than was the case for forward sliding, it is difficult to see why this should be so. However it is likely to be a result of local changes in the radial clamping stress at the fragment ends, where the effects of Poisson contraction/expansion in both fibre and matrix, and plasticity in the matrix are most marked.

Conclusions

The in situ monitoring using synchrotron X-rays of the fibre strain within a Ti-6Al-4V/matrix coated single SCS6 SiC model composite while strained at room and elevated temperature has been used to determine the interfacial properties as a function of position. Before and after fragmentation the point-to-point fibre strain distribution was mapped along the fibre in 10 μm steps. The fine spatial resolution made it possible to form a detailed picture of the fibre/matrix interfacial shear stress distribution and to follow changes in the efficiency of interfacial stress transfer as the temperature was increased. The main findings are summarized as follows:

i) The initial residual fibre strain distribution peaked at $\sim 3200 \times 10^{-6}$ in compression. This is consistent with an axial fibre stress of 1300MPa compression and a clamping radial stress of

around 330MPa. This would be generated by a temperature drop of around 530°C.

ii) Upon plastic straining, multiple fibre fragmentation was detected and the fibre strain distribution was subsequently mapped at 25, 125 and 245 °C. Under load the individual fibre fragment profiles were triangular in shape across the range of temperatures, indicating a constant frictional sliding stress. No evidence was found for a significant mechanical or chemical bond which must be broken prior to sliding. As the temperature was increased the rate of build up of fibre strain in individual fragments decreased and hence the maximum fibre strain measured was lower.

iii) The interfacial shear stress distributions for each temperature were calculated from the fibre strain distributions. In the longer fragments it was possible to identify plateau or constant values of shear stress. Average values for the frictional sliding stress, estimated from the plateau values, are presented as a function of temperature in Table 1. As the temperature was increased the level of the frictional sliding stress decreased indicating a decrease in the efficiency of fibre/matrix interfacial stress transfer mechanisms. This rate of decrease in interfacial shear stress is somewhat quicker than one would expect given the initial stress free effective temperature. It is consistent with the observations by Zeng et al. for SCS-6/Timetal 834 [13] but steeper than observed by Ghosn et al. [14] for SCS-6/Ti-24-11 and Ti-15-3 which tended to fall to zero towards 700°C.

Table 1 Average interfacial friction sliding stress values as a function of temperature

Temperature (°C)	Interfacial Shear Stress (MPa)	Standard Deviation (MPa)
25	150	55
125	100	55
245	35	38

iv) The residual strain distribution after unloading of the sample exhibited ‘w’ profiles for the longer segments and ‘v’ profiles for the shorter ones. It appears that the shear stresses are lower upon unloading than during loading.

We believe these are the first direct measurements of load transfer between an individual fibre and the matrix in-situ, giving rise to unique measurements of the variation of interfacial shear stress along fibre fragments as a function of temperature.

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